

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Testing Concrete with FLEX TPS

The following Application Highlight addresses testing of concrete using the C-Therm Trident™. The document highlights the use of bulk thermal conductivity testing on porous samples with the TPS method.

Researchers, engineers, and students in the field of concretes, cements, geopolymers and similar materials need to tune their products' thermal properties to the application in question, to optimize energy efficiency and control thermal strain. Too low thermal conductivity can result in a large temperature gradient between opposite ends of the material in application, resulting in thermal strain and cracking. On the other hand, a very high thermal conductivity can make it difficult to control the internal temperature.

To maximize efficiency in construction, a variety of lightweight concretes have been developed to decrease weight of walls and foundations without losing much strength. However, these lightweight concretes often are more porous than their standard analogs, resulting in changes to the effective thermal conductivity. To counteract these changes and ensure the new lightweight formulations will still pass heat-transfer requirements, additives are often added to tune the thermal properties.

The following highlights basic setup instructions and example data for testing concrete samples.

Figure 1. Concrete sample setup for testing with Trident FLEX TPS

To begin, obtain two identical pieces and sandwich the Trident TPS FLEX sensor between them, as shown above. Set power and time settings in the Trident software, collect and analyze the data according to best practices for TPS data analysis.¹

¹ International Standards Organization (ISO). 2015. *ISO 22007-2: Plastics — Determination of thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity — Part 2: Transient plane heat source (hot disc) method.*

Between each test, wait until the sample returns to equilibrium. For most concretes, this will take approximately 5-10 minutes.

Figure 2. Data collection on concrete samples using Trident FLEX TPS (n=10).

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com